

**Politecnico
di Torino**

Direzione Ricerca,
Rapporti con l'Impresa e Innovazione

Writing tips for Horizon Europe collaborative proposals with a focus on impact

A PRACTICAL GUIDE ON HOW TO WRITE THE IMPACT SECTION
IN HE PROPOSALS

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Disclaimer

This is an unofficial document prepared by the Research, Technology Transfer and Innovation Department of POLITO.

The information contained in this document is intended to assist and support POLITO researchers who plan to submit a project proposal within the Horizon Europe funding framework. It does NOT substitute European Commission Documents, which in all cases must be considered as official and binding.

The purpose of this handbook is to support POLITO researchers in the process of **writing the impact section of Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs) and Innovation Actions (IAs)**, providing hints and practical examples that can be used for proposals writing. Nevertheless, **in this handbook you will not find details on the other two criteria: 'excellence' and 'quality and efficiency of the implementation'**.

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Introduction

This manual focuses on **proposals for research ideas presented in response to the second pillar of Horizon Europe**, namely the 6 Clusters **Health, Culture, creativity and inclusive society, Civil security for society, Digital, industry and space, Climate, energy and mobility, Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment** (in the orange box):

* The European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) is not part of the Specific Programme

Figure 1 – Horizon Europe Structure. Source: HE Programme Guide

Horizon Europe (HE) is the EU's key funding programme for Research and Innovation with a budget of €95.5 billion. This Programme - the 9th Framework Programme - running from 2021 to 2027, has a different genesis from his predecessors: for the first time the European Commission has delivered a Strategic Plan (implementing act) to prepare the work programmes containing the calls for the first four years of the programme setting the policy priorities for investing in research and innovation. The first Strategic Plan (2021-2024) has been followed by an Implementation strategy that has, among its objectives, «**Maximising impacts**» of the research and innovation programme. Here we can find evidence of the importance of the impact of research funded by the EU.

Then the second Horizon Europe strategic plan¹ for the period 2025-2027 specifies that “Only by disseminating and actually using [*read exploiting*] excellent research results will the EU be ready to

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Horizon Europe strategic plan 2025-2027*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/092911>, page 42.

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face the future. **Dissemination and exploitation (D&E) are key** to supporting the translation of results into knowledge, goods and services of economic and societal value.”

In a nutshell, what is impact? Within your project you will obtain some **results** (which may be, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc.) that through **communication, dissemination and exploitation** will generate an impact. Impact corresponds to the measurement of the **benefit** originated from the **innovation**, which is the result of your research project. As a consequence, is crucial to, first, identify your project results and, then, to use them in the best way possible.

So impact is very important in order to:

1. Justify research, which is financed with public funds;
2. Share and avoid duplication, to guarantee that there is a benefit for all EU citizens and, by making research results open, making them available for further research;
3. Increase knowledge to support European and National policies and decisions in all areas.

Chapter I - Proposal structure

As previously said, this manual focuses on the proposal structure for research ideas presented in response to the second pillar of Horizon Europe which is the following:

Application form (Part A)

- 1 General information
- 2 Participants
- 3 Budget
- 4 Ethics and Security
- 5 Other questions

web-based forms, generated by the IT system on the basis of the information entered by the participants

Project proposal - Technical description (Part B)

- 1 Excellence
- 2 Impact
- 3 Quality and efficiency of the implementation
- Annexes to proposal part B (additional information that may be requested for some calls)

Page limit applies

Figure 2 – Horizon Europe II pillar projects structure.

Source: own elaboration

Regarding the proposal page limit, in Horizon Europe there is a substantial **reduction in maximum length**:

- RIAs and IAs type of actions: limit for a full application is 45 pages. For topics using lump sum funding, the limit is 50 pages.
- CSAs: limit is 30 pages. For topics using lump sum funding, the limit is 33 pages.
- First stage proposals: limit is 10 pages.

Exceptions, if any, would be specified in the call text.

Please note that the page limit will be applied automatically, which means that **additional pages will be automatically cut off**.

Please note that when preparing a proposal for Part B **participants have to use a call/topic specific template provided directly in the submission system**.

All two-stage calls in 2023 and 2024 will take part in the Pilot on **Blind evaluation** (except justified cases) during the first stage application.

NEW admissibility criterion: applicants submitting a proposal under the blind evaluation pilot must **not disclose their organisation names, acronyms, logos nor names of personnel** in Part B of their first-stage application. This means that if proposals include any identification of the applicant in Part B, the proposal will be declared inadmissible.

In particular:

Part A

The IT system will automatically hide from experts the identification (consortium) data in the Proposal Details page.

Part B

It is up to the applicant to omit there any identification data in their first-stage application.

Please refer to the ad-hoc guidance prepared by our Department, available here: [https://mypoli.polito.it/intra/sartt/Finanziamenti Europei Regionali Nazionali.asp?id_documento_padre=224889](https://mypoli.polito.it/intra/sartt/Finanziamenti_Europei_Regionali_Nazionali.asp?id_documento_padre=224889)

In the process of proposal writing do not forget the following horizontal topics:

Figure 3 – Horizontal topics in Horizon Europe. Source: EC

Pay attention to the **additional eligibility conditions** fixed for each HEU topic, set out in the table *Specific conditions* at the beginning of each topic.

Example: topic security HORIZON-CL3-2023-DRS-01-05

<i>Eligibility conditions</i>	<p>The conditions are described in General Annex B. The following exceptions apply:</p> <p>The following additional eligibility criteria apply:</p> <p>This topic requires the active involvement, as beneficiaries, of at least two first responders' organisations or agencies, and one representative of local or regional authorities in charge of disaster response, from at least 3 different EU Member States or Associated Countries. For these participants, applicants must fill in the table "Information about security practitioners" in the application form with all the requested information, following the template provided in the submission IT tool</p> <p>If projects use satellite-based earth observation, positioning, navigation and/or related timing data and services, beneficiaries must make use of Copernicus and/or Galileo/EGNOS (other data and services may additionally be used).</p>
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Figure 4 – Eligibility conditions. Source: Work Programme 2023-2024 Civil Security for Society

Chapter II - How to write a proposal step-by-step

1. Understand the logical framework behind the Horizon Europe programme
2. Read carefully the destination description and the topic description

Build the roots
of your proposal

3. Brainstorming

4. Write the proposal!

Create your
proposal!

STEP 1 – Understand the logical framework behind the Horizon Europe programme

Horizon Europe Legislation² defines **three types of impact**, which are based on three EU grand objectives.

Moreover, these impacts will be tracked with nine **Key Impact Pathways (KIP)**. These 9 KIPs will be used to measure and monitor the IX Framework Programme³, namely Horizon Europe.

In the following you can find an image depicting these important elements:

² See Horizon Europe Regulation, Article 50 and Annex V 'Time-bound indicators to report on an annual basis on progress of the Programme towards the achievement of the objectives referred to in Article 3 and set in Annex V along impact pathways'

³ In April 2023 the EC has developed an ad-hoc framework to monitor and evaluate the framework programme: <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-05/swd-2023-132-monitoring-evaluation-he.pdf>

SCIENTIFIC IMPACT

Promote scientific excellence, support the creation and diffusion of high-quality new fundamental and applied knowledge, skills training and mobility of researchers, attract talent at all levels, and contribute to full engagement of Union's talent pool in actions supported under the Programme

- Creating high quality new knowledge
- Strengthening human capital in R&I
- Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open Science

SOCIETAL IMPACT

Generate knowledge, strengthen the impact of R&I in developing, supporting also implementing Union policies, and support the uptake of innovative solutions in industry, notably in SMEs, and society to address global challenges, inter alia the SDGs

- Addressing EU policy priorities & global challenges through R&I
- Delivering benefits and impact via R&I missions
- Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society

ECONOMIC IMPACT

Foster all forms of innovation, facilitate technological development, demonstration and knowledge transfer, and strengthen deployment of innovative solutions

- Generating innovation-based growth
- Creating more and better jobs
- Leveraging investments in R&I

Figure 5 – Impacts set in Horizon Europe Legislation

In Horizon Europe there is an important novelty: the **Strategic Plan**⁴ which sets the strategic orientations for the targeting of investments in the programme's first four years (2021-2024). It

⁴ The Horizon Europe strategic plan is the product of a series of intense co-creation activities among Commission services and co-design activities with Member States, members of the European Parliament, stakeholders and citizens at large. This has taken place through successive rounds of public consultations, web surveys and interactive workshops, in particular during the annual Research and Innovation Days (June 2021).

The EC has already published the "Horizon Europe strategic plan analysis 2025-2027, the analytical foundation for the second Strategic Plan: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/0e3caad8-5b8f-4f01-a422-39e14ce9052b_en. The Strategic Plan 2025-2027 is expected to be adopted in 2024.

ensures that EU research and innovation actions contribute to EU priorities⁵. This plan identifies four **Key Strategic Orientations (KSOs)**:

Figure 6 – Key Strategic Orientations. Source: [Strategic Plan](#)

Each of the key strategic orientations encompasses three to four cross-cutting **impact areas**, which in turn link to a number of **expected impacts**. These expected impacts define the wider effects on society, the economy and science to be targeted by research and innovation activities, but not the manner in which to achieve them. This is up to the applicants when designing their project proposals.

In total, the strategic plan defines **32 expected impacts** that cover a wide range of social, economic, ecological and scientific aspirations. Each expected impact serves as the foundation for a

⁵ Six Commission priorities for 2019-2024 (https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024_en):

- A European Green Deal
- A Europe fit for the digital age
- An economy that works for people
- A stronger Europe in the world
- Promoting our European way of life
- A new push for European democracy.

corresponding destination in the relevant **work programme** parts of Horizon Europe's second Pillar, 'Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness'.

In brief, the impact implementation of Horizon Europe is done according to the elements contained in the following image:

Figure 7 – Horizon Europe logical framework. Source: own elaboration

Example: in the following you can find an extract from Strategic Plan related to Cluster 5 Climate, Energy and Mobility 2021-2022

KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS FOR R&I	KSO A: Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital, enabling and emerging technologies, sectors and value chains	KSO C: Making Europe the first digitally enabled circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy
IMPACT AREAS	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	Climate change mitigation and adaptation Affordable and clean energy Smart and sustainable transport Circular and clean economy
EXPECTED IMPACTS	<p>16. Clean and sustainable transition of the energy and transport sectors</p> <p>25. Climate-neutral and environmental-friendly mobility</p>	<p>21. Transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society and economy</p> <p>23. Efficient, clean, sustainable, secure, and competitive energy supply</p> <p>24. Efficient and sustainable use of energy</p> <p>26. Safe, seamless, smart, inclusive, resilient, climate neutral and sustainable mobility systems</p>

Figure 8 – Cluster 5. Source: [Strategic Plan](#)

Regarding the EU Policy Priorities you can refer the [Strategic Plan Analysis](#) (2021-2024), which displays for each Cluster and each thematic area the ‘Relevant EU policy objectives’ and ‘Studies and other scientific evidences, including from EU-funded research’, as you can see from the extract below:

Horizon Europe pillar/part	Relevant EU policy objectives	Studies, other scientific evidence and relevant initiatives at EU level (including institutionalised partnerships)
Cluster 1	<p>Overarching EU goals and commitments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Pillar of Social Rights, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/social-summit-european-pillar-social-rights-booklet_en.pdf, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/priorities/deeper-and-fairer-economic-and-monetary-union/european-pillar-social-rights/european-pillar-social-rights-20-principles_en Political guidelines for the next Commission (2019-2024) - "A Union that strives for more: My agenda for Europe", 	<p>Studies and other scientific evidences, including from EU-funded research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In silico Clinical Trials: How Computer Simulation will Transform the Biomedical Industry, Viceconti, Marco & Henney, Adriano & Morley-Fletcher, Edwin. (2016). DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.2756.6164, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289522507_in_silico_Clinical_Trials_How_Computer_Simulation_will_Transform_the_Biomedical_Industry Setting research priorities in environment and health, Report of a meeting in Cascais, Portugal 27–28 April 2017; http://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0020/340733/Binder1.pdf?ua=1

Figure 9 – Extract from Horizon Europe Analysis, pag. 14

STEP 2 – Read carefully the destination description and the topic description

Example: below you will find samples from the Cluster 5 Climate, Energy and Mobility 2021-2022 and the relative analysis.

<i>Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2021-2022 Climate, Energy and Mobility</i>	
Global leadership in renewable energy	239
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-01: Innovative components and/or sub-systems for CSP plants and/or concentrating solar thermal installations	239
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-02: Best international practice for scaling up sustainable biofuels	240
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-03: Efficient and circular artificial photosynthesis	241
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04: Integrated wind farm control	242
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-05: Novel Thin Film (TF) technologies targeting high efficiencies	244
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-06: Efficient and low-emission technologies for industrial use of combustion and gasification systems from low-value biogenic residues and wastes	246
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-07: Development of algal and renewable fuels of non-biological origin	247
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-08: Development of digital solutions for existing hydropower operation and maintenance	248
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-09: Recycling end of life PV modules	249
Destination – Efficient, sustainable and inclusive energy use	251
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Highly energy-efficient and climate neutral EU building stock	256
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-01: Advanced energy performance assessment and certification	256
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-02: Industrialisation of deep renovation workflows for energy-efficient buildings	258
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-03: Advanced data-driven monitoring of building stock energy performance	261
Industrial facilities in the energy transition	264
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-04: Full-scale demonstration of heat upgrade technologies with supply temperature in the range 90 - 160°C	264
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-05: Industrial excess (waste) Heat-to-Power conversion based on organic Rankine cycles	266
Call - Efficient, sustainable and inclusive energy use	267
Conditions for the Call	268
Highly energy-efficient and climate neutral EU building stock	269
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-02-01: Demonstrating integrated technology solutions for buildings with performance guarantees (Built4People)	269
HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-02-02: Cost-effective, sustainable multi-functional and/or prefabricated holistic renovation packages, integrating RES and including re-used and recycled materials (Built4People)	271

CLUSTER (previously called Work programme)

Each Cluster is made up of several Destinations

DESTINATION:

each destination is connected with one of the **Expected impacts** indicated in the Strategic Plan, which defines the **political/strategical orientation** and describes **socio-economic challenges** to be faced and the related expected impacts to which the research and innovation activities will contribute.

TOPICS

Destination – Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods

This Destination includes activities addressing safe and smart mobility services for passengers and goods.

Europe needs to manage the transformation of supply-based transport into safe, resilient and sustainable transport and demand-driven, smart mobility services for passengers and goods. Suitable research and innovation will enable significant safety, environmental, economic and social benefits by reducing accidents caused by human error, decreasing traffic congestion, reducing energy consumption and emissions of vehicles, increasing efficiency and productivity of freight transport operations. To succeed in this transformation, Europe's ageing (and not always sustainable) transport infrastructure needs to be prepared for enabling cleaner and smarter operations.

Europe needs also to maintain a high-level of transport safety for its citizens. Resilience should be built in the transport systems to prevent, mitigate and recover from disruptions. Research and innovation will underpin the three safety pillars: technologies, regulations and human factors.

This Destination contributes to the following Strategic Plan's **Key Strategic Orientations (KSO)**:

- *C: Making Europe the first digitally enabled circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems;*
- *A: Promoting an open strategic autonomy²²⁷ by leading the development of key digital, enabling and emerging technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations.*

It covers the following **impact areas**:

- Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people;
- Smart and sustainable transport.

The **expected impact**, in line with the Strategic Plan, is to contribute to *"Safe, seamless, smart, inclusive, resilient and sustainable mobility systems for people and goods thanks to user-centric technologies and services including digital technologies and advanced satellite navigation services"*, notably through:

- a. Accelerating the implementation of innovative **connected, cooperative and automated mobility (CCAM)** technologies and systems for passengers and goods (more detailed information below).
- b. Further developing a **multimodal transport system** through sustainable and smart long-haul and urban freight transport and **logistics**, upgraded and resilient **physical and digital infrastructures** for smarter vehicles and operations, for optimised system-wide network efficiency (more detailed information below).
- c. Drastically decreasing the number of **transport accidents, incidents and fatalities** towards the EU's long-term goal of moving close to zero fatalities and serious injuries by 2050 even in road transportation (Vision Zero) and increase the **resilience** of transport systems (more detailed information below).

KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS, as set out in the Strategic Plan, wide orientations for research and innovation

EXPECTED IMPACT, as set out in the Strategic Plan, which is brought here again in order to help participants contribute with the research and innovation activities of the project.

For each of these three elements (a, b, c) there is a list that details the expected impacts.
Example b Multimodal and sustainable transport systems for passengers and goods:

The main impacts to be generated by topics targeting Multimodal and sustainable transport systems for passengers and goods under this Destination are:

- Upgraded and resilient physical and digital infrastructure for clean, accessible, affordable, connected and automated multimodal mobility.
- Sustainable and smart long-haul, regional and urban freight transport and logistics, through increased efficiency, improved interconnectivity and smart enforcement.
- Reduced external costs (e.g. congestion, traffic jams, emissions, air and noise pollution, road collisions) of urban, peri-urban (regional) and long distance freight transport as well as optimised system-wide network efficiency and resilience.
- Enhanced local and/or regional capacity for governance and innovation in urban mobility and logistics.

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-12: Controlling infection on large passenger ships

Specific conditions	
<i>Expected EU contribution per project</i>	The Commission estimates that an EU contribution of between EUR 3.00 and 5.00 million would allow these outcomes to be addressed appropriately. Nonetheless, this does not preclude submission and selection of a proposal requesting different amounts.
<i>Indicative budget</i>	The total indicative budget for the topic is EUR 8.00 million.
<i>Type of Action</i>	Research and Innovation Actions
<i>Technology Readiness Level</i>	Activities are expected to achieve TRL 5 by the end of the project – see General Annex B.

Expected Outcome: Project outputs and results are expected to contribute to all of the following expected outcomes as applicable for the two sub-activities:

- Communicable infections (Covid-19, influenza, norovirus) do not spread rapidly amongst passengers and crew on large passenger ships, in particular on cruise ships. The spread is controllable also beyond the vessel in ports and port communities.
- Communicable infections on board large passenger ships can be detected systematically at an early stage and effective measures are put in place to prevent the spread of infection. Crews and other personnel are duly trained.
- Large passenger ships are intrinsically designed to prevent the spread of infection and to facilitate measures in case of detection to eliminate further spread.
- An evidence base is established concerning the specific mechanisms facilitating the on-board spread of infection and the effectiveness of different mitigation methods.
- A knowledge base is publicly available concerning mechanisms facilitating the spread of on-board infection, mitigation measures and underlying evidence.
- Evidence based guidance for healthy passenger ship design is available to improve the design of ships which can help avoiding infections and facilitate the detection on board infections at an early stage, inherently mitigate the spread of infection and facilitate actions to prevent its further spread.

Scope: Passenger ships and in particular cruise ships (with their high occupancy rates and elevated passenger and crew numbers of up to 8000 persons, close proximity of passengers and crews, high crew turnover with crews coming from many different countries, frequent port calls naturally implying common shore side excursions, and on-board activities with intense social interaction) have been implicated in the spread and multiplication of disease. Large and medium-sized cruise ships have seen a highly dynamic and sometimes dramatic multiplication of Covid-19 infections on-board and the disembarkation of several hundred

Each TOPIC is composed of three sections:

SPECIFIC CONDITIONS (table): topic peculiarities in terms of budget, type of action, TRL and *additional eligibility conditions* (if any).

EXPECTED OUTCOMES: list of specific results and expected impact in the short term, which (in turn) contribute to the medium and long term impacts stated in the Destination and in the Strategic Plan.

SCOPE: brief description, illustrating current situation and future needs, containing prescriptive directions and cross-cutting recommendations (SSH, gender, international cooperation, synergies, ...)

infected (and often asymptomatic) passengers who subsequently became vectors for infection within the regions concerned and their home regions. In this context it needs to be kept in mind that cruise passengers often travel to and from the ship by air, adding to the potential spread. Passenger ships have also been hosts for the rapid spread of Norovirus illness, influenza and legionella infections. This can be particularly problematic for (generally smaller) passenger ships that undertake longer expedition-type cruises away from population centres, thus entirely or predominantly relying on on-board medical services and facilities. Europe as the world's largest and almost exclusive producer of large and medium-sized passenger and cruise ships and as home to a large number of important cruise destinations must ensure a healthy on-board environment which is also crucial for the viability and the sustainable growth of the business. Whilst guidelines to control the spread of on-board infections have been published, it is clear that these are not fully effective and there is a lack of an evidence base to underpin the effectiveness of the suggested measures for different infections. Important knowledge gaps continue to exist and so far the real effectiveness of different mitigation measures now deployed remains largely anecdotal.

To address these challenges, proposals will address one of the following two aspects and cover all of the tasks mentioned.

1. "Infection control on-board large passenger ships - prevention, mitigation and management".

[..]

2. "Healthy ship design":

[..]

This topic requires the effective contribution of SSH disciplines and the involvement of SSH experts, institutions as well as the inclusion of relevant SSH expertise, in order to produce meaningful and significant effects enhancing the societal impact of the related research activities.

In these two phases (step 1 and step 2), Politecnico's Collaborative and Multi-disciplinary Research Planning Division (**RIMIN**) is also available to support researchers in background and call text analysis. Moreover, it is possible to contact the National Contact Points (**NCP**) for further support – usually RIMIN is the subject in charge of this connection.

STEP 3 – Brainstorming

Undertake a brainstorming session (with colleagues, researchers in other fields, administrative personnel, etc) to develop your ideas for research.

- Define the relevance of your project idea to the EU call
- Identify key stakeholders and needs.
- Define the consortium.
Pay attention: partner search is time consuming!
- Review of the current situation – scientific and technology.

Do your preparatory research! Do not set as first work package something like 'literature review' because you should already know it, before the writing phase. Moreover, search for

last projects funded under similar calls on CORDIS (the primary source of results from EU-funded projects since 1990, <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects/en>).

- Develop the project concept.
- Start to think about the project acronym and check if already used.

In order to check if the acronym you developed has been already used you can start by checking if there is already an EU project with the same acronym on <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects>, then you can simply double check by searching on the internet 'the acronym of your project+EU project' in order to see if the acronym has already been used.

STEP 4 – Start write your proposal!

Since the impact represents the measurement of the benefits deriving from innovation, we suggest to **start writing your proposal from the impact section**. It is good to adopt the *reverse thinking*:

Figure 10 – Reverse thinking. Source: own elaboration

In order to help you identify the different types of impact your project could have, it is possible to start from the following image:

Figure 11 – European Science Foundation Impact Classifications

Chapter III - Write the impact section

Practical implications following the new impact logic set in HEU

We suggest to start from the table **Impact summary** (table 2.3) in order to help you develop your project idea, then write the whole proposal (excellence and implementation sections and impact 2.1 and 2.2) and, finally, revise table 2.3 enriching it with all the elements that come out during the proposal writing.

2.1 Project's pathways towards impact

This section will contain examples based on the topic HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-13: *Safe automation and human factors in aviation – intelligent integration and assistance* (thus linked to Cluster 5 Climate, Energy and Mobility (Destination Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods). You will find these examples in green boxes, following the points of the Horizon Europe template.

- (a) How the project's results are expected to make a difference with respect to:
- the **expected outcome** specified in the topic (medium term)

Example: Innovative accessibility and logistics solutions applied by the European air transport sector

- the wider **impacts** (expected impact), in the longer term, specified in the respective destination in the work programme.

Example (expected impact of Destination 6 Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods): "Safe, seamless, smart, inclusive, resilient and sustainable mobility systems for people and goods thanks to user-centric technologies and services including digital technologies and advanced satellite navigation services"

Then identify the problem/need to address.

Example: Most airports use process flow-oriented models based on static mathematical values limiting the optimal management of passenger flow and hampering the accurate use of the available resources to the actual demand of passengers.

As a consequence, define which will be the results that you expect your project will generate.

Example: Successful large-scale demonstration trial with 3 airports of an advanced forecasting system for proactive airport passenger flow management

Identify and describe the **target groups** that would benefit from your project.

*Example: Target group: airport managers and all those involved in the Airport Operations Management
End users: travelers*

Be specific, breaking target groups into particular interest groups or segments of society relevant to your project.

(b) Provide quantified estimates of the project's contribution to the expected outcomes and impacts. Consider:

- **Scale** = how widespread the outcomes and impacts are likely to be.

For example, in terms of the size of the target group, or the proportion of that group, that should benefit over time;

- **Significance** = the importance, or value, of those benefits. For example, number of additional healthy life years; efficiency savings in energy supply.

Good practice (from an evaluator comment on a proposal that received a score of 4,5 points): The scale and significance of the expected outcomes is convincing and is appropriately quantified by setting key performance indicators (KPIs).

Example: the project expected contribution to

- *The expected outcome is the adoption of the advanced forecasting system demonstrated during the project by at least 9 European airports*
- *The expected impacts are two:*
 - *economic impact -> the increase of the max passenger capacity by 15% and passenger average throughput by 10%, leading to a 28% reduction in infrastructure expansion costs;*
 - *scientific impact -> new breakthrough scientific discovery on passenger forecast modelling.*

Where relevant, explain how the potential harm can be managed.

Applicants can here refer to the **DNSH principle** to show that their project will not carry out activities that make a significant harm to any of the six environmental objectives of the EU Taxonomy Regulation⁶.

Example: ProjectXX is not expected to significantly harm any of the environmental objectives set out in Article 9 of the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation. Furthermore, the project will even contribute to the objective (a) "climate change mitigation" of this Article 9, by developing a novel

⁶ The EU Taxonomy Regulation 2020/852 establishes six environmental objectives (Article 9):

- climate change mitigation,
- climate change adaptation,
- sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources,
- transition to a circular economy,
- pollution prevention and control, and
- protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.

At project level, proposers can refer to the DNSH principle when presenting their **research methodology** (section 1 Excellence) and the **expected impacts of the project** (section 2.1). However, evaluators will not score applications in relation to their compliance with the DNSH principle unless explicitly stated in the work programme.

technology with a very high decarbonisation potential. In any case, each partner is well-aware of the “do no significant harm” principle and will ensure to respect and comply with its criteria.

(c) Describe any **requirements** and potential **barriers** that may determine whether the desired outcomes and impacts are achieved.

Consider:

- Economical, e.g. high initial investment for the adoption of the proposed solution or process of the materials used in the project;
- Political, e.g. lack of involvement and support from government authorities;
- Legislative, e.g. complexity from the regulatory point of view because legal frameworks are very different within each EU country;
- Social, e.g. acceptance of the solution developed.

Describe any mitigating measures you propose, within or beyond your project, that could be needed should your assumptions prove to be wrong, or to address identified barriers.

Note that this section does not include the critical risks inherent to the management of the project itself, which should be described below in Section 3 ‘Quality and efficiency of the implementation’.

Example: Potential barriers to ProjectXX spread

In the following table you can find an analysis⁷ in order to take into account diverse factors that can affect negatively the Projects’ results deployment in the market

Legal and regulatory factors	Economic factors
<p><i><u>Option 1:</u> Future EU regulations could ban the usage of ... (used and necessary in the project), which would limit the development potential of the technology. However, ProjectXX will limit the amount of .. so that the required performances still can be guaranteed, and the safety can be maintained.</i></p> <p><i><u>Option 2:</u> The development of ProjectXX components and systems will lead to outcomes that are in strong conformity with the relevant standards. Of special importance are regulations on (i) ... (ii) ... (iii) Also, to keep the proposed developments current, the consortium will constantly monitor legal</i></p>	<p><i><u>Option 1:</u> The eventual infrastructure costs will be kept low by integrating the forecasting systems in the platforms already used by Airport Operations Management.</i></p> <p><i><u>Option 2:</u> In case of a project on electric vehicles an important economic factor is energy prices: European countries have different legal regulations regarding the connection to the electrical grid of power-generating facilities. These facilities must comply with certain procedures to guarantee that the whole system fits supply and demand. ProjectXX is sensitive to fluctuations in market prices and demand thus it has been taken every reasonable step to</i></p>

⁷ This analysis can be carried out using the PESTLE approach, which stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors. It is a Business Analysis technique used to examine various factors that affect the market environment for a business or organization.

<i>changes during the project lifetime and adopt any process, if required.</i>	<i>account for variations in the process of constructing the business model.</i>
Social factors (e.g. user behavior)	Technological factors
<i>Final end-users have to be aware of their role. In this sense, a co-creation process will be considered within ProjectXX to involve future customers in all the phases of the project development. The advancements achieved will be properly disseminated and communicated to achieve an engagement in initiatives that require customer implication.</i>	<i>Barrier to adopt the new forecasting systems, due to the lack of certification activities. To safeguard the adoption of its deployment, the project has prompted to test the system and demonstrate the applicability and efficiency within 3 airports. Moreover the project is already involving a standardization body in order to ease the adoption of the forecasting system.</i>

2.2 Measures to maximise impact - Dissemination, exploitation and communication

The implementation of the previous programme (Horizon 2020) showed that beneficiaries often confuse the concepts of dissemination, communication and exploitation. The image below can help you to clarify the differences and apply these concepts:

Figure 12 – Communication, dissemination & exploitation definitions. Source: EC slide

Communication in art. 17 of GA Annex 5 + visual identity (display the of EU flag)

Dissemination in art.17 of GA Annex 5

Exploitation in art. 14 of GA Annex 5 + IPR in art. 16

What's new in Horizon Europe about DEC?

- D&E is part of the Key Impact Pathway to demonstrate the contribution to the impact on society
- Continuous reporting on D&E (even after the end of the project)
- Emphasis on exploitation. In fact:
 - Horizon Europe encourages the use of the R&I results through third party exploitation (where appropriate);
 - The follow up of the exploitation activities will continue after the end of the project;
 - If during the first year after the end of the project, despite the best effort for exploitation, no exploitation takes place, beneficiaries must use the [Horizon Results Platform](#) for making their exploitable results visible (unless obligation is waived). The Horizon Results Platform is free, is part of the F&T portal, available to all beneficiaries and is based on results, not on projects.

As in H2020, since at the **proposal stage** is too early to know what kind of results you will have, you are expected to present a **plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities**. Unless otherwise specified in the call conditions, you will be asked to submit a **detailed plan** at the latest **6 months after the date of signature of your grant agreement** (deliverable).

In the proposal you should take in to account the **capacity and role of each consortium member**, and the extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise to carry out the DEC activities (avoid any overlaps with section 3.2 *Capacity of participants and consortium as a whole*). The suggestion we give to Coordinators is to allocate for each participant some resources (within the budget) to take part in Communication and Dissemination activities for the project.

Dissemination and Exploitation measures

- Have to be proportionate to the scale of the project
- Must contain concrete actions (e.g. stakeholders management, business and market actions, standardisation, spin-off, etc.) to be implemented both during and after the end of the project
- Planned according to draft timeline of when they will reach their own outcomes/impact both during and after the project

To help you identify the best way to exploit (that is use) your results, the European Commission has published a document that contains a toolbox that identifies and analyse the main channels for knowledge (research and innovation results and data) valorisation⁸:

Figure 13 – Mapping of actors, channels and tools. Source: EC publication

Communication measures

- Adequate to promote the project and its findings throughout the full lifespan of the project
- Strategically planned with clear objectives
- That clearly define the main message, tool(s) and channel(s) that will be used to reach out to target groups
- To promote your project and its results beyond the projects own community
- To communicate your research in a way that is understood by non-specialist, e.g. the media and the public
- To inform EC in advance of communication activities expected to have a major media impact.

Elements of the DEC plan:

- **Communication measures** for promoting the project and its findings throughout the full lifespan of the project

⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Research & innovation valorisation channels and tools – Boosting the transformation of knowledge into new sustainable solutions*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/480584>

- **Planned measures** to maximise the impact of projects
- **Target groups** (e.g. scientific community, end users, financial actors, public at large) and suitable **channels** to interact
- **Policy feedback measures** to contribute to policy shaping and supporting the implementation of new policy initiatives and decisions
- **Follow-up plan** to foster exploitation/uptake of the results
- **Strategy for the management of the intellectual property.**

The provision of a results ownership list (ROL) is mandatory at the end of the project.

In the following image you can find a set of questions that will help you identify the DEC measures:

Figure 14 – Communication, dissemination & exploitation. Source: EC slide (with further elaboration)

Example: DEC measures

- 1) Exploitation: *patenting the algorithmic model*
Dissemination towards the *scientific communication and airports: scientific publication with the results of the large-scale demonstration*
Communication: *an event in a shopping mall to show how the outcomes of the action are relevant to our everyday lives;*
- 2) Exploitation: *patenting the new product; licencing to major electronic companies*
Dissemination towards the *scientific communication and industry: participating at conferences; developing a platform of material composition for industry; participation at EC project portfolios to disseminate the results as part of a group and maximise the visibility vis-à-vis companies.*

2.3 Summary

The last paragraph is represented by a table, which is a new element compared to the Horizon 2020 template.

It is actually a table that summarizes the whole section 2 *Impact* and it is done according to the logic of the Business Model Canvas, where in the different boxes you describe the added value of what you propose and the relation between the different elements represented by the boxes.

SPECIFIC NEEDS	EXPECTED RESULTS	D & E & C MEASURES
<i>What are the specific needs that triggered this project?</i>	What do you expect to generate by the end of the project?	What dissemination, exploitation and communication measures will you apply to the results?
TARGET GROUPS	OUTCOMES	IMPACTS
<i>Who will use or further up-take the results of the project? Who will benefit from the results of the project?</i>	<i>What change do you expect to see after successful dissemination and exploitation of project results to the target group(s)?</i>	<i>What are the expected wider scientific, economic, societal effects of the project contributing to the expected impacts outlined in the respective destination in the work programme?</i>

Sum up of the previous two sections of the proposal

Figure 15 – Table ‘Key element of the impact section’. Source: EC template

In particular, in the following image you can find the correspondence between the proposal template sections and the different parts of the table:

SPECIFIC NEED	EXPECTED RESULTS	DEC MEASURES	TARGET GROUPS	OUTCOMES	IMPACTS
Section 1 Excellence	2.1 Project's pathways towards impact	2.2 Measures to maximise impact • DisseminationExploitation&Communication strategy and plan • IPR and knowledge strategy		2.1 Project's pathways towards impact a) and b)	
Section 2 Impact					

Figure 16 – Correlation between the template sections and the summary table in section 2.3. Source: own elaboration

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di Torino**

Direzione Ricerca,
Rapporti con l'Impresa e Innovazione

The specific need your project is responding to, that is the project's added value, should emerge from section Excellence while all the other boxes are, as previously stated, the summary of section 2 Impact.

The suggestion given by the evaluators is to keep **the table in one page**, given the fact that is a summary, and in order to show that you have clear in your mind what your project will bring (and the road to take to reach it!).

Chapter IV - During the project's lifetime

The renewed importance of research results can be seen also in the implementation phase of the research projects: in the **reporting**. In fact, Horizon Europe has introduced better and more focused D&E reporting (**NEW** in all HE proposals) as follows:

- Results table

Name	Result type	Key results (KER) <i>(does result have a high potential?)</i>	Description of high potential* <i>(max. 200 characters)</i>	Audience or target group*	Steps undertaken towards exploitation** <i>(multiple choice)</i>	Market maturity** <i>(state of the market targeted by this result)</i>
[name]	[SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory (...)] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)] [PO — Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy] [EVNT — Event (conference, seminar, workshop)] [STAFF — (qualified personnel exchanges)] [LEARN — learning and training (learning modules, curricula)] [INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities]	[High scientific potential] [High societal potential (other than climate or environmental)] [High societal potential] [High technologic, business or economic potential] [High policy or regulatory potential] [N/A]	[insert description]	[Researchers] [Industry, business partners] [Investors] EU Institutions and/or agencies] [Policy makers and authorities, international] [Policy makers and authorities, national] [Policy makers and authorities, regional or local] [Citizens] [Standardization bodies] [Innovators] [End users (practitioners, farmers, etc)] [Education/training organization/ learners] [Research Infrastructures] [Business accelerator providers] [Other] [Applicable to all]	[Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstration or testing] [Intellectual property management] [Complying with regulatory framework] [Contribution to standards] [Feasibility Study] [Market Study] [Business plan] [Other]	[Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created] [Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market] [Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply] [Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products]

▪ Results Ownership List

Results ownership list						
Continuous Reporting (Results ownership list screen) — Indicate the owner(s) of the results.						
Note:						
This is the 'results ownership list' required under the Grant Agreement.						
The submission of your last Periodic Report will be blocked if this table is not filled in.						
Single or joint ownership of results? <i>(Indicate the number of owners)</i>	Result owners	Owner country of establishment	Will the owners exploit the result?	In which form will the result be made available to other consortium members and/or third parties?	Does the exploitation of the results require access to background of one or several consortium members? <i>(If Yes a compulsory question opens below)</i>	Does the exploitation of the results require access to third party IPR? <i>(If Yes, a compulsory question opens below)</i>
[number of owners]	[insert owner name(s)] <i>[Entity or Individual]</i> <i>Entity: Drop down option with project partners + 'Other'. 'Other' opens a field asking for name, address, country, and an identifier such as VAT number.</i> <i>Individual: Drop down option with 'researchers in project'</i>	[country]	[YES] [NO]	[Sale of IP] [Licensing] [Open access] [Open source] [Free license] [Secret/non-disclosure agreement] [Other] [N/A]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO] [NOT KNOWN]
Exploitation requires access to background of consortium members						
[insert measures taken /envisaged to give access to the background required for exploitation]						
Exploitation requires access to third party IPR						
[insert measures taken /envisaged to get access to the required IPR]						

Dissemination activities

Dissemination activities				
<i>Continuous Reporting (Dissemination screen) — List the dissemination activities carried out in the context of the project. Include dissemination activities mentioned in the proposal and new ones.</i>				
Dissemination Activity Name	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience <i>(Choose one or more items)</i>	Why? <i>(max 200 characters)</i>	Status
[insert activity name]	[Conferences] [Education and training events] [Meetings] [Clustering activities] [Collaboration with EU-funded projects] [Other scientific collaboration] [Other]	[Industry, business partners] [Investors] [EU institutions] [Policy-makers and authorities, international] [Policy-makers and authorities, national] [Policy-makers and authorities, regional or local] [Civil society, international] [Civil society, national, regional or local] [Public] [Standardization bodies] [Scientists] [Innovators] [Specific end-user communities] [Education/training organization/learners] [Other]	[insert description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output]	[Delivered] [Cancelled] [Postponed] [Ongoing]

Communication activities

Communication activities					
<i>Continuous Reporting (Communication screen) — List the communication activities carried out in the context of the project. Use the same labels used in your DEC plan.</i>					
Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience <i>(Choose one or more items)</i>	How? Communication channel <i>(Choose one or more items)</i>	Outcome	Status
[insert communication name]	[insert description of implemented communication activity]	[Industry, business partners] [Innovators] [Investors] [EU institutions] [National authorities] [Regional authorities] [Local authorities] [Civil society] [Citizens] [Research communities] [Specific user communities (if applicable)] [International organization (UN body, OECD etc)]	[Website] [Social media] [Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners etc)] [Press release] [Media article] [Newsletter] [Interview] [Video] [TV/Radio campaign] [Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc)] [Exhibition] [Other]	[insert key performance indicators]	[Delivered] [Cancelled] [Postponed] [Ongoing]

Figures 17 a, b, c, d – Periodic Report. Source: EC

Chapter V - Preview of the future

The [Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027 Analysis](#) published on the 25 of May 2023 explores the current status of R&I in the EU and evaluates what changes would be required in light of the first Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2021-2024. The respondents provided feedback or suggestions for improving the structure, language and presentation of the previous Strategic Plan. In particular, the analysis underlines the need to simplify the structure reducing the number of layers (KSO, clusters, impacts, etc.), use more accessible language, and make the Plan more concrete. Suggestions for improvement include:

- Better describe impact areas and expected impacts
- Reduce the number of impacts / prioritise the importance of the expected impacts
- Better explain the difference between impact/results, outputs/deliverables
- Provide definitions of the terms used
- Avoid using official or technical jargon
- Use the same terminology in the Strategic Plan as in the work programmes
- Add charts to help to understand the structure
- Add infographics / visuals to summarise the main messages.

Figure 16. How easy is it to understand the four Key Strategic Orientations (KSOs) of the Horizon Europe's 2021-2024 Strategic Plan?

Source: European Commission (2023), *Synopsis Report - Looking into the R&I future priorities 2025-2027*, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023.

Figure 18 – How easy is to understand the four KSOS? Source: Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027 Analysis, pag. 46

As a consequence, in the near future we might see some modification to the 4 KSOs we are used to see inside the Work programmes.

Following the highlighted need to simplify the structure of Horizon Europe, the Strategic Plan 2025-2027⁹, that is the second Horizon Europe Strategic Plan, provides **three key strategic orientations** for R&I activities in 2025-2027, that are:

- Green transition
- Digital transition
- A more resilient, competitive, inclusive and democratic Europe.

These key strategic orientations are the guiding principles **for all parts of Horizon Europe** and will be implemented through the work programmes 2025-2027.

Moreover, the second strategic plan does not display impact areas but, instead, focus on the expected impacts each Cluster aims to achieve. A very interesting overview is provided within the Strategic Plan:

Figure 19 – Expected Impacts for Horizon Europe.
Source: Horizon Europe, the Strategic Plan 2025-2027, pag. 8

⁹ See note no. 1.

Annex 1 - Definitions

Let's clarify some confusing concepts!

In the following you will find the definitions according to Horizon Europe Template:

Deliverable	A report that is sent to the Commission or Agency providing information to ensure effective monitoring of the project. There are different types of deliverables (e.g. a report on specific activities or results, data management plans, ethics or security requirements).
Impacts	<p><u>Wider long term effects</u> on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments (long term). It refers to the specific contribution of the project to the work programme expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur some time after the end of the project.</p> <p>Example: <i>The deployment of the advanced forecasting system enables each airport to increase maximum passenger capacity by 15% and passenger average throughput by 10%, leading to a 28% reduction in infrastructure expansion costs.</i></p>
Outcomes	<p>The <u>expected effects, over the medium term</u>, of projects supported under a given topic. The results of a project should contribute to these outcomes, fostered in particular by the dissemination and exploitation measures. This may include the uptake, diffusion, deployment, and/or use of the project's results by direct target groups. Outcomes generally occur during or shortly after the end of the project.</p> <p>Example: <i>9 European airports adopt the advanced forecasting system demonstrated during the project.</i></p>
Pathway to impact	Logical steps towards the achievement of the expected impacts of the project over time, in particular beyond the duration of a project. A pathway begins with the projects' results, to their dissemination, exploitation and communication, contributing to the expected outcomes in the work programme topic, and ultimately to the wider scientific, economic and societal impacts of the work programme destination.
Research output	Results generated by the action to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, data or other engineered outcomes and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols and electronic notebooks.
Results	<p>What is <u>generated during the project implementation</u>. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc.) are 'Intellectual Property', which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal 'Intellectual Property Rights'.</p> <p>Example: <i>Successful large-scale demonstrator: trial with 3 airports of an advanced forecasting system for proactive airport passenger flow management.</i></p>

Figure 20 – Relation between results, outcomes and impacts. Source: EC slide 9 June 2021

Key exploitation result(s) (KER) is defined as:

- “a main result which has been prioritised due to its high potential for exploitation and further scientific, societal or policy use” within the periodic report template available on the EC site¹⁰,
- “an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education” within the Horizon Results Booster¹¹.

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

¹¹ <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/HEU%20Results%20platform.pdf>

Annex 2 - Impact logic example

Horizon Europe impact implementation with an example created by the EC:

Figure 21 – HEU implementation. Source: EC slides

Another way to see the same info (but displayed in a different way):

Figure 22 – HEU implementation. Source: EC slide 21 April 2021

Annex 3 - Impact section from RIA and IA projects template

2.1 Project's pathways towards impact [e.g. 4 pages]

- Provide a **narrative** explaining how the project's results are expected to make a difference in terms of impact, beyond the immediate scope and duration of the project. The narrative should include the components below, tailored to your project.
 - (a) Describe the unique contribution your project results would make towards (1) the **outcomes** specified in this topic, and (2) the **wider impacts**, in the longer term, specified in the respective destinations in the work programme.
 - (b) Give an indication of the scale and significance of the project's contribution to the expected outcomes and impacts, should the project be successful. Provide quantified estimates where possible and meaningful.
 - (c) Describe any requirements and potential barriers - arising from factors beyond the scope and duration of the project - that may determine whether the desired outcomes and impacts are achieved. These may include, for example, other R&I work within and beyond Horizon Europe; regulatory environment; targeted markets; user behaviour. Indicate if these factors might evolve over time. Describe any mitigating measures you propose, within or beyond your project, that could be needed should your assumptions prove to be wrong, or to address identified barriers.

2.2 Measures to maximise impact - Dissemination, exploitation and communication [e.g. 5 pages, including section 2.3]

- Describe the planned measures to maximise the impact of your project by providing a first version of your 'plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities'. Describe the dissemination, exploitation and communication measures that are planned, and the target group(s) addressed (e.g. scientific community, end users, financial actors, public at large).
- Outline your strategy for the management of intellectual property, foreseen protection measures, such as patents, design rights, copyright, trade secrets, etc., and how these would be used to support exploitation.

2.3 Summary

SPECIFIC NEEDS <i>What are the specific needs that triggered this project?</i>	EXPECTED RESULTS <i>What do you expect to generate by the end of the project?</i>	D & E & C MEASURES <i>What dissemination, exploitation and communication measures will you apply to the results?</i>
TARGET GROUPS <i>Who will use or further up-take the results of the project? Who will benefit from the results of the project?</i>	OUTCOMES <i>What change do you expect to see after successful dissemination and exploitation of project results to the target group(s)?</i>	IMPACTS <i>What are the expected wider scientific, economic and societal effects of the project contributing to the expected impacts outlined in the respective destination in the work programme?</i>

Annex 4 - Evaluation template

Extract from the Evaluation form for RIAs, IAs and CSAs related to the section 2. Impact

2. Impact	
The following aspects will be taken into account, to the extent that the proposed work corresponds to the description in the work programme:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Credibility of the pathways to achieve the expected outcomes and impacts specified in the work programme, and the likely scale and significance of the contributions from to the project.	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities.	
Comments:	
Score 2 (0-5): Threshold: 3/5	

'Scale' refers to how widespread the outcomes and impacts are likely to be. For example, in terms of the size of the target group, or the proportion of that group, that should benefit over time;

'Significance' refers to the importance, or value, of those benefits. For example, number of additional healthy life years; efficiency savings in energy supply.

Explain your baselines, benchmarks and assumptions used for those estimate.

Annex 5 - Evaluators' assessment

In the evaluation process, the **evaluators are given some slides** to help them assessing the Impact section. In the following, you will find the bullet points for Impact:

Assess the proposed pathways towards impact:

- Is the contribution of the project towards the 1) expected outcomes of the topic and 2) the wider impacts, in the longer term, as specified in the respective destinations of the WP, credible?
- Are potential barriers to the expected outcomes and impacts identified (i.e. other R&I work within and beyond Horizon Europe; regulatory environment; targeted markets; user behavior), and mitigation measures proposed? Is any potential negative environmental outcome or impact (including when expected results are brought at scale, such as at commercial level) identified? Is the management of the potential negative impacts properly described?
- Are the scale and significance of the project's contribution to the expected outcomes and impacts estimated and quantified (including baselines, benchmarks and assumptions used for those estimates)?
 - 'Scale' refers to how widespread the outcomes and impacts are likely to be. For example, in terms of the size of the target group, or the proportion of that group, that should benefit over time;
 - 'Significance' refers to the importance, or value, of those benefits. For example, number of additional healthy life years; efficiency savings in energy supply.

Source: The [Horizon Europe Proposal Evaluation briefing](#) (guidance for evaluators)